

COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING OF CORROSION PROCESS IN MEDICAL IMPLANT SURFACES

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Abstract

Researchers apply different techniques to control the possible reactions between implant material surfaces and living tissues to prevent harmful corrosion defects by increasing life quality. However, corrosion process is difficult to predict experimentally, due to its complexity. Therefore, numerical simulations with predictive purpose can be used to estimate structural damage of biomedical implants. This paper focuses on implementation of cellular automata (CA) in computational modelling of corrosion process in medical implant surfaces. The model consists of two sub-models – pit initiation and pit growth model and a set of rules that define the change of states through time. The results are shown to describe well the progress of corrosion. Future steps would include the inclusion of experimentally obtained material properties and validation of results against experiments.

Key words: cellular automata (CA), discrete modelling, corrosion, coating, implant surfaces

1. Introduction

Materials such as stainless steels, cobalt-chromium based alloys, commercial titanium, and Ti6Al4V, commonly used in implant materials, may face an aggressive corrosion environment including blood and other constituents of the body fluid. Therefore, corrosion resistance is one of the most important factors that affect the efficiency of an implant material that is to be used in the body. There have been many attempts on the corrosion resistance of conventional metallic implant materials during the last decade, either through simulations or with case studies. Coating the implant surfaces with a biocompatible coating is a common approach in controlling the possible reactions between living tissues and implant material surfaces [1].

2. Methods and Results

Evolution of CA each cell occurs through a series of synchronous updates of all cells, governed by a set of rules [2]. The problem of computational modelling of multi-pit corrosion in medical implants based on cellular automata is divided into pit initiation and growth models. The state of the cell is represented by a predefined interval in the range of 0 – 255, where un-corroded cell has

the value of 0 and totally corroded cell the value of 255. In initiation model, each cell x is associated with an initiation potential state $I(u, t) = I(u, t - 1) + \alpha$ at time t . For each un-corroded cell u , initiation potential state values in its Von Neumann neighborhood together with its own is considered $I(u, t) + \sum I(u + \delta_i, t)$ and if that sum over 3 overcomes the threshold value, then a corrosion pit is initiated at cell u and its corrosion state $S(u, t)$ is set to a small positive number between 3 and 5. For the next time steps, pit initiation model is applied on the uncorroded cells again, and at the same time pit growth model is applied on the cells where corrosion has been initiated with formula:

$$S(t + 1, x) = S(t, x) + k_1 f[S(t, x)] + k_2 \sum_i f[S(t, x + c_i)] + k_3 \sum_j f[S(t, x + d_j)] + k_4 \Delta \quad (1)$$

where $c_i = (0, -1), (1, 0), (0, 1), (-1, 0)$, $d_j = (1, 1), (1, -1), (-1, -1), (-1, 1)$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and $k_1 = \lambda \times (pH - 7)^2 \times \text{step}(4, 8.5) \times e^{\varphi_M - \varphi_S} \times (1/T) \times C \times D \times z$ [2]. In these eq. λ is a discount factor ranges from 1 to 3; pH is the pH value of the solution; $\text{step}(4, 8.5)$ is a function with value 0 between 4 and 8.5, and 1 otherwise; φ_M and φ_S are the potentials of the metal and solution, respectively; T is the absolute temperature; C is the concentration of the reaction species; D is the diffusivity of the reaction species; z is the charge of the reaction species. The parameters k_2 , k_3 and k_4 are in similar forms as k_1 , but with different discount factors. Results show that the model describes adequately the multi-pit corrosion pit initiation and growth. Fig. 1 shows the corrosion states at four different time steps, where black indicates uncorroded cell white indices fully corroded cell. The results are well comparable with [2].

Fig. 1. Corrosion state $S(u, t)$ at time steps $t = 2, 3, 4, 5$

3. Conclusions

Model has a good basis and has been tested against different parameters to confirm stability of the solution. In future, simulation results will be validated against the experimental data through a comparison analysis of frequency histogram distribution on the image pixel value and eqs. for $k_1 - k_4$ will be redefined to suit better to the problem of biocompatible implant surface corrosion.

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